

Use of Cloud-based Communication and Management Tools for Service Delivery in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology Minna

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Abstract

This study examined the use of cloud-based communication and management tools for service delivery in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology Minna. The study was guided by three objectives. A survey research design was adopted. The population comprised twenty-four academic librarians, and total enumeration was used. Data were collected using a questionnaire and observation checklist and analysed using descriptive statistics. Findings revealed the availability of several communication tools including WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, email services, Zoom, and Ex-Libris Cloud, alongside management tools such as institutional repositories, website hosting services, OCLC, Greenstone, and DSpace. Results also showed a generally high level of utilisation, particularly for WhatsApp Mean score \bar{x} of 3.33, email services with Mean score \bar{x} of 3.47, institutional repositories with Mean score \bar{x} of 3.38, OCLC with Mean score \bar{x} of 3.38, and website hosting services with Mean score \bar{x} of 3.52 respectively, while Koha and Amazon Web Services were either unavailable or underutilised. In addition, the findings further identified challenges such as unreliable power supply, insufficient policies for using cloud services and poor technological facilities in library. The study concluded that cloud-based technologies significantly enhance service delivery. It recommended the adoption of additional cloud management platforms, continuous staff training and Strengthen Power and ICT Infrastructure to improve effective utilisation.

Key words: Service delivery, cloud-based communication tools, Cloud-based management tools, cloud computing

Introduction

The emergence of cloud-based technologies has significantly reshaped the landscape of information service delivery in academic libraries across the globe. Advances in information and communication technologies (ICTs) have transformed university libraries from traditional, print-

centred institutions into dynamic, digitally driven information hubs that support teaching, learning, and research beyond physical boundaries (Sharma, 2015). In this digital era, cloud-based communication and management tools have become indispensable for enhancing accessibility, efficiency, and responsiveness in library services.

Cloud computing refers to the provision of computing services including software, storage, processing power, and communication tools over the internet, eliminating the need for local installation and extensive hardware infrastructure (Mohammed & Zeebareec, 2021). Cloud-based communication tools such as email, WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and other web-based platforms operate largely under the Software as a Service (SaaS) model, enabling libraries to interact with users in real time and deliver services remotely (Chudasma *et al.*, 2019). These tools support information dissemination, reference services, current awareness services, and user education, thereby improving user engagement and satisfaction (Agu *et al.*, 2022).

In university libraries, the adoption of cloud-based management tools has further strengthened internal workflows and service delivery mechanisms. Integrated Library Systems (ILS) such as Koha, Polaris, and Ex Libris Cloud provide web-based solutions for cataloguing, circulation, acquisitions, and user management, ensuring seamless access to library resources regardless of location (Roy & Kumar, 2017; Chahare, 2024). Similarly, institutional repositories hosted on cloud infrastructure enable libraries to preserve, manage, and disseminate scholarly outputs such as Theses, Dissertations, and research publications, thereby increasing the visibility and impact of institutional research (Asadi *et al.*, 2019; Oyadeyi & Fasola, 2022).

The Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) model further enhances library service delivery by offering scalable computing and storage resources through platforms such as Amazon Web Services (AWS). This approach allows libraries to manage increasing volumes of digital content, ensure data security, and accommodate fluctuating user demands, particularly during peak academic periods (Suleiman, 2021; Okike & Omali, 2023). Cloud-hosted websites also enable libraries to maintain uninterrupted access to online services while reducing operational costs associated with physical servers (Wada, 2018).

The Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library of the Federal University of Technology (FUT), Minna, serves a technology-oriented academic community that relies heavily on timely access to digital information resources. As a result, the effective use of cloud-based communication and management tools is essential for meeting the information needs of students, researchers, and academic staff. These tools not only support efficient service delivery but also enhance the library's capacity to remain relevant in an increasingly digital academic environment.

Despite the proven benefits of cloud-based technologies in academic libraries, their availability and level of utilisation vary across institutions, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria. Assessing the types of cloud-based communication and management tools available and the extent to which they are used in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library is therefore crucial. Such an assessment provides empirical insight into how cloud technologies contribute to effective information service delivery and informs strategies for improving library services in line with global best practices.

Statement of the Problem

The integration of cloud-based communication and management tools has become essential for enhancing efficiency, accessibility, and quality of service delivery in academic libraries. These technologies support real-time communication, remote access to information resources, digital cataloguing, and effective management of library operations. However, in many developing countries, including Nigeria, the adoption and effective utilisation of cloud-based services in university libraries remain uneven and inadequately documented. Challenges such as infrastructural deficiencies, limited technical expertise, inconsistent power supply, funding constraints, and weak institutional policies have continued to impede optimal deployment and sustainability of these technologies (Enefu & Okpala, 2023).

Although Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology Minna, has reportedly introduced certain cloud-based tools to support communication and management functions, there is insufficient empirical evidence regarding the specific tools available and the extent to which they are effectively utilised for service delivery. The absence of such data creates a gap in understanding the actual impact of these technologies on library performance and user satisfaction. Consequently, there is a need to systematically examine the availability and level of utilisation of cloud-based communication and management tools in the library to inform strategic planning, policy development, and improved service delivery.

Objectives

The aim of this study is to investigate the Use of Cloud Base Communication and Management Tools for Service Delivery in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology Minna. To achieve this aim, the following specific objectives were outlined to guide the study:

- i. identify the types of cloud-based communication and management tools available in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology, Minna;
- ii. determine the level of use of cloud-based communication and management; tools in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology, Minna; and
- iii. identify challenges affecting the use of cloud-base services in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology, Minna.

Concept of Service Delivery

service delivery involves the giving of assistance to a user who is searching for electronic, digital and other related information within a particular library (Oden & Owolabi 2021). It was identified that user education services, inter-library loan services, abstracting services, cataloguing services, reprographic services, bibliographic services, circulation services, reference services and information services are some of the services delivered in university libraries.

Cloud-Based Communication Tools in Libraries

Cloud base communication tools are software applications and associated services to users over the Internet eliminate the need for local installation and maintenance. Examples include, web-based applications like Hotmail, Google Apps, and Skype, as well as Web 2.0 solutions like Facebook, Twitter, and Flickr (Chudasma *et al.*, 2019). In the context of libraries and information centers, SaaS facilitates accessibility and usage of various software tools and platforms. Characteristics outlined by Mohammed and Zeebareec (2021) include continuous access to services, hosting applications in third-party premises, and availability of services through web interfaces.

Cloud computing represents a transformative technological advancement that enables global connectivity, allowing users to access software and hardware resources remotely. “It is an emerging technology that allows anyone to be connected with rest of the world in order to use software and hardware which are distantly apart” (Sharma, 2015). Cloud base communication tools like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, and WhatsApp emerge as a fascinating example, not only as a messaging apps but as a paradigm of cloud-based service delivery. The integration of cloud-based applications like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, and WhatsApp into university libraries exemplifies the transformative impact of cloud computing on information service delivery. These tools can therefore be applied in university libraries for information distribution and communication for effective information service delivery (Agu *et al.*, 2022). Facebook, with its comprehensive social networking features, allows libraries to create and maintain dynamic online communities. Through Facebook, libraries can facilitate discussions, share updates, and promote events, thereby fostering a sense of community and enhancing user engagement.

Email, as a cloud computing application, serves as a fundamental tool for enhancing information service delivery in university libraries. By leveraging cloud-based email services, libraries can facilitate effective communication and information sharing among staff, students, and faculty, which is critical for meeting the diverse needs of their users (Chahare, 2024).

Cloud-Based Communication Tools in Libraries

Automation Applications represent a critical advancement in library management, thereby offering cloud-based solutions that streamline various library operations. By leveraging cloud computing, these applications facilitate real-time updates and remote access to library systems, which is crucial for improving service delivery and operational efficiency. Library automation involves the use of computing applications and information technology to manage bibliographic control, access databases, share resources, and facilitate electronic communication. Its aim is to improve and enhance the services provided to library users (Western New York Regional Information Center (WNYRIC), 2019).

Koha is an open-source Integrated Library System (ILS) widely adopted for its flexibility and comprehensive feature set. Koha offers modules for cataloguing, circulation, and acquisitions, all accessible through the cloud (Roy and Kumar, 2017). This enables university libraries in Nigeria to manage their collections, user interactions, and resources efficiently while reducing the need for extensive local IT infrastructure.

Ex Libris Cloud provides a suite of cloud-based library management tools designed to enhance research and learning environments. This platform supports various functionalities, including automated cataloguing, resource management, and user services (Chahare, 2024). By utilising Ex Libris Cloud, libraries can benefit from advanced analytics and seamless integration with other academic systems, thus optimising service delivery and operational workflows.

Polaris is a cloud-based library management system that integrates various library functions, such as cataloguing, circulation, and user management. Polaris library system is one of the cloud-based library automation system available in the world (Okwoli, 2023). Polaris is designed to improve library efficiency through its intuitive interface and robust cloud capabilities, thereby enabling libraries to offer more streamlined and responsive services to their patrons.

The adoption of SaaS solutions like Koha, Ex Libris Cloud, and Polaris significantly enhances the delivery of information services in university libraries across Nigeria as Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library Federal University of Technology in particular. These platforms offer scalable, flexible, and efficient tools for managing library operations, improving user access to resources, and ensuring the effective preservation and dissemination of information.

Institutional repositories function as digital archives that compile and preserve an institution's intellectual outputs. They not only protect these outputs but also facilitate their exploration and dissemination in various digital formats (Asadi *et al.*, 2019). An institutional repository is a set of services that a university or organisation provides to the people in its community for the administration and sharing of digital content produced by the institution and people in the community (Henok and Yule, 2019). Digital outputs are collected and curated in institutional repositories. Institutional repositories increase the exposure and influence of a university's or institution's research outputs by making them available to the public (Oyadeyi and Fasola, 2022). The adoption of IaaS in university libraries can significantly bolster the effectiveness of institutional repositories. By utilising cloud-based IaaS, libraries can access scalable storage solutions to manage the increasing volume of digital content, streamlining data management and ensuring easy access to research papers, theses, dissertations, and other academic resources.

Amazon Web Services (AWS) provides a robust solution for delivering on-demand, ready-to-use resources (Suleiman, 2021). As a leading provider in the cloud computing space, AWS pioneered the pay-as-you-go model, enabling users to access comprehensive infrastructure and resources as needed. AWS services encompass a wide range of categories, including Compute, Storage, Database, Data Management, Migration, Hybrid Cloud, Networking, Development Tools, Monitoring, Security, Analytics, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) (Suleiman, 2021). This flexibility empowers university libraries to leverage IaaS, offering scalable computing resources that can be adjusted according to demand, thus facilitating effective management of varying workloads, especially during peak periods like exams or the introduction of new digital resources.

Website services allow libraries to utilise virtualised computing resources via the cloud, eliminating the need for physical servers (Wada, 2018). This model provides essential flexibility and scalability, enabling libraries to adjust their resources according to demand, particularly during high-traffic times such as registration periods. IaaS promotes cost efficiency by allowing libraries to pay only for the resources they consume, while also ensuring strong security, automated

backups, and seamless integration with other cloud services (Okike and Omali, 2023). Ultimately, this approach enhances accessibility and drives innovation in the libraries' digital offerings.

Empirical Studies on Cloud Technology in Libraries

Okwoli (2023) investigated "Security Concerns Associated with the Application of Cloud Computing Services in Federal University Libraries in Nigeria", guided by ten specific objectives. Utilising a survey research design, the study targeted a population of 2,883 librarians across federal universities, with a targeted sample of 340 professional librarians and heads of ICT units responsible for cloud administration, selected through multi-stage sampling from six geopolitical zones. Data collection instruments included questionnaires, interview guides, and observation checklists, with data analysed using descriptive statistics and Spearman's rank order correlation to test hypotheses at the 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed widespread availability of basic cloud-based communication applications and management tools such as WhatsApp, Facebook, KOHA, OCLC, and various email services, while noting non-subscription to Ex-Libris cloud services. The study also identified common infrastructural challenges like power outages, poor internet connectivity, unstable wireless networks, and low ICT knowledge among staff, and recommended that library management should consider subscribing to more advanced hybrid cloud solutions, install network firewalls, and improve security configurations within their cloud networks.

Adejo (2024) conducted research on the "Use of Cloud Computing Technology by Librarians at University of Nigeria Nsukka Library" aimed to determine the devices used, reasons for adoption, extent of use, and information services provided through cloud computing technology in the library. The study employed a descriptive survey research design with a quantitative approach, the research utilised a semi-structured interview questionnaire and involved a population of ten (10) individuals, including the University Librarian and nine digital librarians from the ICT unit. Findings revealed that web-mail services were the most utilised cloud computing service, with significant implementation in cataloguing, metadata, storage, retrieval, and generation. The study recommended the introduction of cloud computing across all university campuses, ongoing training for library staff, adequate budget allocation for cloud activities, and making the library's cloud computing achievements available online to enhance public patronage.

Enefu and Okpala (2023) conducted a study titled "Challenges Affecting the Application of Cloud Computing Services in Federal University Libraries in Nigeria." The study sought to identify the key challenges hindering the effective application of cloud computing services and to determine the measures adopted to mitigate these challenges in federal university libraries across Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was employed for the study. The population comprised 2,883 librarians working in federal university libraries, from which a sample of 340 professional librarians and Heads of ICT units was drawn from six selected federal universities. A multistage sampling technique was adopted, categorizing institutions according to the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria to ensure equitable representation. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and observation checklists, and were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. The findings revealed several major challenges affecting the application of cloud computing services, including inadequate ICT expertise, poor internet connectivity, erratic power

supply, shortage of ICT personnel, insufficient funding, unstable wireless networks, and the high cost of cloud-based services

Research Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design. Population of the study consists of 24 academic librarians in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library Federal University of Technology Minna. Total enumeration was used because the population is manageable. The instruments used were a structured questionnaire and an observation checklist.

Results and Discussion

A total of twenty-four 24 copies questionnaires were administered to the respondents however, 21 copies were filled, returned and found usable for the analysis which represents 88% returned rate. Data were analysed using frequency tables, percentages, Mean and standard deviation, and the weighted Mean scores were used to arrive at a final decision.

Table 4.1: Types of Cloud-Base Communication and Management Tools Available in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology, Minna

Table with 2 columns: Cloud base communication tools, Not available (x) Available (v). Rows include WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter Account, KOHA, Ex-Libris Cloud, Gmail/Yahoo/Hot Mail, Zoom, Institutional repositories, Amazon Web Service, Website Services, OCLC, Green stone, Dspace.

Source: Field work, 2024; Keys: Not available (x) Available (v)

Table 4.1 presents the types of cloud-based communication and management tools available in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology (FUT) Minna, based on field data collected. The findings show that all cloud-based communication tools are available in the library thus are: WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, Ex-Libris Cloud, Gmail/Yahoo/Hotmail, and Zoom. This suggests that while the library has embraced several cloud-enabled communication platforms for outreach and service interaction, not all integrated library management systems are deployed in cloud mode. The availability of widely used communication platforms such as WhatsApp, email services, and social media indicates a strong orientation toward user engagement, real-time communication, and remote service support.

With respect to cloud-based management tools, the table shows that Institutional Repositories, Website Services, OCLC, Greenstone, and DSpace are available, while KOHA and Amazon Web Services (AWS) are not available. This pattern indicates that the library relies more on specialized library and information management platforms rather than general cloud infrastructure services. The presence of multiple digital management tools (Greenstone and DSpace), alongside OCLC for cataloguing and resource sharing, reflects a significant commitment to digital content management, bibliographic control, and global resource visibility. relatively high level of availability of both communication and management cloud tools, positioning the library to support modern digital and remote information services. These findings are consistent with those of Okwoli (2023), which also reported the widespread availability of general cloud base communication and cataloguing tools such as WhatsApp, Facebook, OCLC and various email services in Federal University Libraries in Nigeria.

Table 4.2: Level of Use of Cloud-Base Communication and Management Tools in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology, Minna

Table with 5 columns: Cloud Base Communication and Management Tools, VHE (4), HE (3), LE (2), VLE (1), N, FX, Mean, Std. Dev., Decision. Rows include WhatsApp, Facebook, and Twitter usage metrics.

sharing real-time updates or announcement?	7 (33.3)	10 (47.6)	4 (19)	-					Low
The use of Ex-Libris Cloud in your library for efficient library management and enhanced service delivery.					21	66.00	3.14	.72703	
To what level would you rate the use of Yahoo/Gmail/Hot mail to offer effective current awareness service for library users?	11 (52.4)	9 (42.9)	1 (4.8)	-					High
To what level is the use of Institutional repositories in managing and delivering digital content in your library?					21	73.00	3.47	.60159	
To what level is the use of Institutional repositories in managing and delivering digital content in your library?	11 (52.4)	8 (38.1)	1 (4.8)	1 4.8					High
How would you rate the use Website Hosting services for maintaining and delivering the library's web presence?					21	71.00	3.38	.80475	
How would you rate the use Website Hosting services for maintaining and delivering the library's web presence?	11 (52.4)	10 (47.6)	-	-					High
How would rate the use of OCLC for cataloguing and resource sharing in your library?					21	74.00	3.52	.51177	
How would rate the use of OCLC for cataloguing and resource sharing in your library?	9 (42.9)	11 (52.4)	1 (4.8)	-					High
How would rate the use of OCLC for cataloguing and resource sharing in your library?					21	71.00	3.38	.58959	
How would rate the use of OCLC for cataloguing and resource sharing in your library?	5 (23.8)	14 (66.7)	2 (9.5)	-	21	66.00	3.14	.57321	Low

To what level is Greenstone used for managing and delivering digital collections and library resources?

	8	9	4	-					Low
How would you rate the use of DSpace for managing and providing access to digital assets in your library for effective information service?	(38.1)	(42.9)	(19.0)						
Weighted Average Mean	3.23				21	67.00	3.19	.74960	

Key: Very High Level (VHL) = 4, High Level (HL) = 3, Low Level (LL) = 2, Very Low Level (VLL) = 1

Table 4.2 indicates that the level of use of cloud-based communication and management tools in the Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology Minna is generally high, as reflected by the overall weighted mean of 3.23 from 21 respondents. Tools with high levels of use include website hosting services (Mean = 3.52, SD = .512), email platforms such as Yahoo/Gmail/Hotmail for current awareness services (Mean = 3.47, SD = .602), institutional repositories (Mean = 3.38, SD = .805), OCLC for cataloguing and resource sharing (Mean = 3.38, SD = .590), and WhatsApp for immediate user communication (Mean = 3.33, SD = .730), indicating strong adoption of platforms that support information dissemination and user engagement. These findings are consistent with the findings of Adejo, (2024) which revealed that web-mail services were the most highly utilised cloud computing in university libraries. These findings indicate that, even within a well-resourced university setting in Nigeria, the primary cloud services employed by librarians are centered around communication (email, webmail) and basic data storage, which are foundational to effective information service delivery and information management.

Table 4.3 Challenges Affecting the Use of Cloud-Base Services in Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology, Minna

Table with 9 columns: Statements, SA (4), A (3), D (2), SD (1), N, Mean, Std.D, Decision. Rows include: The power supply is unreliable in my library, There are insufficient policies for using cloud-base management and communication, Poor internet connectivity limits the use of cloud services in my library, Poor technological facilities, and Weighted Average Mean (3.23).

Keys: Strongly Agreed (SA) = (4), Agreed (A) = (3), Disagreed (D), = (2) Strongly Disagreed (SD) = (1)

The analysis of responses from Table 4.3 indicates that several key factors affect the use of cloud-based services in the library. The results shows that respondents agreed that unreliable power supply (Mean = 3.2381; SD = 0.94365) constitutes a significant challenge, underscoring the dependence of cloud services on stable electricity. Similarly, insufficient policies guiding the use of cloud-based management and communication tools (Mean = 3.2381; SD = 0.62488) were identified as a constraint, suggesting the need for clear institutional frameworks to regulate implementation and usage. Poor technological facilities (Mean = 3.2381; SD = 0.62488) were also agreed upon as a major limitation, reflecting inadequacies in ICT infrastructure necessary for effective cloud deployment. However, respondents disagreed that poor internet connectivity (Mean = 3.1905; SD = 0.67964) significantly limits cloud service usage, indicating relatively satisfactory internet access within the library. The overall weighted mean of 3.23 demonstrates general agreement that infrastructural and policy-related issues remain the primary barriers to optimal utilization of cloud-based services in the library. The findings of this study are consistent with those of Enefu and Okpala (2023), who examined challenges affecting the application of cloud computing services in federal university libraries in Nigeria. In the present study, unreliable power supply emerged as a significant challenge, a result that directly aligns with Enefu and Okpala’s identification of erratic power supply as one of the major barriers to effective cloud computing adoption. Both studies therefore underscore the critical role of stable electricity in sustaining cloud-based operations. Furthermore, the identification of insufficient policies and poor technological facilities in the present study corresponds with Enefu and Okpala’s findings on inadequate ICT infrastructure, limited ICT expertise, and funding constraints, all of which point to systemic and institutional weaknesses affecting cloud implementation.

Conclusion

The study established that Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology Minna, has adopted several cloud-based communication and management tools that support service delivery. The findings revealed that WhatsApp, email services, institutional repositories, OCLC, and website hosting services are both available and highly utilised, demonstrating the library's commitment to modern, user-centred service provision. However, some important tools like Koha and Amazon Web Services are either unavailable or underutilised. Although the overall level of utilisation is high, disparities in adoption indicate the need for improved infrastructure and staff capacity development to maximise the benefits of cloud-based technologies in library service delivery.

Recommendations

1. The library management should invest in acquiring additional modern cloud-based management tools to strengthen digital infrastructure and service efficiency.
2. Regular training and capacity-building programmes should be organised for librarians to enhance effective utilisation of available cloud-based communication and management tools.
3. The university management should invest in alternative power solutions such as solar energy systems and backup generators, alongside upgrading ICT infrastructure (modern computers, servers, and networking equipment).

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